

A COLLABORATIVE FRAMEWORK FOR MIGRATIONS

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Abstract – We present a framework for mass migration of preserved content, where the owner of the content is a different party than the one which does the migration. This requires a close collaboration between these parties. In Finland, we have a centralized digital preservation service for various organizations (including museums, archives, libraries, universities, research institutes), and thus collaboration between the different organizations and the service provider is crucial to success for preserving content in the long-term, including migrations. We present our first migration project using this framework. This provides a solid base on how such migrations can be performed in the future; especially in our case, but also in a wider context.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Collaboration is a key to success in digital preservation. This is essential through the whole life cycle of digital assets as digital preservation needs to be a dynamic activity in a constantly changing environment. As an example, content migration requires knowledge about the contents of the digital assets, knowledge about how and why the assets have been created and included in a repository, as

well as technical expertise on digital preservation methods.

In Finland we have established a wide and successful model of collaboration [1] to preserve our digital cultural heritage and research data in the National Digital Preservation Services (DPS) for cultural heritage and research data [2]. The model defines a service provider, CSC - IT Center for Science, that produces the national centralized services, provides the infrastructure, technical expertise, and digital preservation expertise on a national level. The service is utilized by partner organizations that are Finnish libraries, archives, museums, universities, and research organizations that own the data. These organizations have an expertise on the actual content of their data, and know the needs of the designated communities that make use of the digital content. Together, all parties participate in defining the specifications and preservation strategies for the services.

The National Library of Finland (NatLibFi) has been harvesting online content since 2006 when the Copyright Act authorised it to preserve content from information networks. The Act on Collecting and Preserving Cultural Materials (1433/2007) has obliged NatLibFi to preserve online content since

2008. The Finnish Web Archive contains a diverse and representative sample of the Finnish internet, the content of the archive considers also the needs of research and the archiving of cultural history. Content is harvested from websites (e.g., HTML) as well as social media platforms (e.g., Twitter, YouTube, Facebook, and TikTok). The collection currently comprises more than 4.3 billion files totalling approximately 300 terabytes. NatLibFi was the first strategic partner to store digital objects using the DPS. The first AIPs were created in 2015 and close collaboration has been ongoing ever since.

Web archiving is a process where websites are preserved using specific tools and the archives are meant to be represented similarly as they were at the time of the capture. This process creates a prominent amount of crawled data, many web archives reaching petabyte-scale. Web crawling software has evolved during the years, and so have the file formats in which the crawls are preserved. The first standard was Internet Archive's ARC format which later was standardized by ISO into WARC (Web ARChive) [3]. In NatLibFi the archiving process during the years has created archives in different archive formats, and content in the older formats were the first ones ingested into the DPS.

The need to harmonize all the different older web archive formats into ISO standardized WARC 1.0 was born because of the large amount of format and version variation in the older content. As the DPS had been planning to create the process to conduct large-scale migrations, these two needs collided and created a possibility to get the web archives harmonized and build a real working process framework for all the future migrations.

Migration frameworks have been introduced also earlier [4]. In this paper, we present the national and collaborative framework for automated migrations and our first mass migration project, where collaboration between organizations is the key.

II. LOGICAL PRESERVATION AS A BASE FOR MIGRATION PLANNING

A successful migration requires planning and a well-defined process. As this project was the first mass migration conducted in the DPS, the process was developed alongside the actual migration. Together with partner organizations, DPS has published specification of requirements for logical preservation [5]. It defines how file formats, technical

metadata, and file format migrations should be handled. Fig. 1 describes logical preservation in relation to semantic and bit-level preservation.

Figure 1. Levels of preservation

The specification identifies a set of requirements for the migration process, including defining migration paths, proper and sufficient planning of the migration process, checks where the results must be approved before the process can continue, and describing the final report for the migration.

The requirements also stipulate responsibilities for both the DPS and the partner organization owning the content. The DPS is, for example, responsible for providing tools for performing the migrations, specifying technical migration paths, performing test migrations and the actual migration, validating the migrated content, and providing results to the partner organization. The partner organization, for example, defines parameters for the migration, taking into account the needs of the designated communities, assesses the results of the test migration, possibly updates metadata, decides on how to proceed, and approves the final results. Both parties produce a report about the migration collaboratively.

The migration can be triggered by both parties. The DPS monitors file formats and their life cycle, and can thus flag that content should be migrated if a file format is in risk of becoming obsolete. Further, the partner organization monitors the designated communities and their needs.

With these logical level requirements, we started mapping out a plan for migrating the ARC/WARC content as a collaborative effort.

III. COLLABORATIVE MIGRATION FRAMEWORK

The collaborative migration framework is described in Fig. 2. The steps are documented

collaboratively in a migration report, which is beneficial to future migrations. The colors in the Figure shows the responsibilities between the partner organization and the DPS.

Figure 2. Collaborative migration framework

Define requirements: The first phase is to create a common understanding of the current situation and expected outcome, including for example metadata updates. In the project, we defined this in several joint meetings. We had more than 600,000 digital objects to migrate, taking about 70 terabytes. It was clear that a manual process was not an option.

Desk research: Exploring experiences of similar migrations by others may give hints, or even provide a proper solution right away. There exists documentation on ARC/WARC migration, confirming that the decision to migrate the content was sound. In the project, no direct documented experience could be applied directly, but for example existing tools were selected for evaluation.

Evaluate tools: At this point, a number of tools with a couple of files are tested manually, looking at the resulting files, and all the impact the tool may have. This may include for example changed values, missing data or metadata, even added metadata by the tool and so on. Reference implementations of the file format standard should be preferred. With manual examination, only a few files can be tested, but at this stage the idea is to find a path that looks promising. In the project, the DPS collected all the findings, and then NatLibFi evaluated them and decided on how to proceed.

Agree on a plan: The partner organization and DPS agree on the plan, which concerns both file format migration and the handling of metadata. In the project, we did not find a single software library

that would have been able to do all of the changes. However, we managed to find a series of libraries that could be used in a sequenced order. It was also decided to append some bibliographical metadata into each WARC file from an external source.

Implement workflow: A fully automated workflow to conduct the migration steps has to be able to select the content to migrate from the DPS, migrate the digital objects, update and possibly enrich content metadata, report errors in the process, technically validate the results, and provide the migrated result to the partner organization for semantic evaluation. In the workflow, new provenance metadata documenting the process is also added. A large-scale migration workflow needs to be able to effectively process a large number of digital objects in parallel.

Provide test sets: For testing the workflow, the partner organization of the DPS needs to select reasonably sized test sets which as a whole represent the full content comprehensively. NatLibFi selected many thematic collections in all the possible different file formats to get a representative sample of crawl products over the times. A thematic collection is a varying number of files representing a crawl dealing with the same subject matter and using these collections makes it possible to use the original crawl seeds later in the quality assurance phase.

Migrate test sets and manage metadata: Testing the migration in a fully automated workflow may reveal for example unforeseen workflow bugs and inconsistencies in the digital objects. In the project, there were both of these. Multiple iterations with several test sets with fruitful discussion between the DPS and NatLibFi increased understanding. DPS was also able to improve the performance of the migration workflow. Content metadata was enriched by specifications from NatLibFi. Provenance information also included information about the original objects.

Quality assurance and approval: Quality assurance is done by the partner organization. If issues are found, the DPS fixes the workflow accordingly. This is done using an iterative testing process, where the test sets are migrated and validated between the parties until the process is fully functional. In NatLibFi, the web archivists compared the output of the migration to the original collection, comparing site look in the browser and sizes of the indexes after

indexing. When some problems or issues were found, actions were taken to overcome them, after which a new test migration was made and results revalidated.

Production process: The partner organization needs to provide a list of the digital objects to migrate for the DPS. If the metadata is enriched, the metadata to be appended is also needed. After this, the whole production process is run by the DPS. This is done in a staging area, separated from the actual preservation system. In the project, NatLibFi delivered a JSONL file with required details and metadata for migration.

Approve results and preserve: In a collaborative process, the migration result is approved by signing the packages. This is done by the partner organization who owns the data. After this, the SIPs are formed and ingested with an automated process. In the project, this approval confirmed that the migration result was accepted by NatLibFi.

IV. CONCLUSION

Successful iteration and development of the process required continuous communication between the DPS and NatLibFi. As a result, a documented framework for future mass migrations was defined. We found out that the requirements specified earlier were pretty accurate. We had several meetings, performed multiple test migrations, and made fixes to the process that resulted in a high quality outcome. The process has to be able to accommodate iterative steps, that allow for both fallbacks to previous steps, and multiple tested iterations of the workflow.

It is crucial that know-how about the content and its uses is utilized in collaboration with technical expertise and digital preservation knowledge. In the project, this was solved by a tight and intensive cooperation between NatLibFi and the DPS.

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